

Whether Artificial Intelligence Image Generators Pose a Threat to Moral Rights for Creative Works in The United States?

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Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of artificial intelligence, a distinctive future known as Image Generator has raised significant legal and ethical concerns in our lives. Image Generators can generate photos and pictures from a person's imagination, as described in the chat input, and produce almost anything using its extensive database that leverages connections to the worldwide web. Theoretically, an image generator can access to any image on its database and create dozens, if not thousands, of different versions of that specific picture, along with meeting the user's demands. In recent years, many scholars have addressed to number of concerns surrounding Artificial Intelligence and copyright. However, there has been limited attention to the risks that image generators pose to moral rights in the United States, which offers limited, narrow and "fragile" moral rights protection. This article delves into the unique framework of moral rights in the United States, examining how AI image generators can potentially infringe those rights and contradict the purpose they serve.

The analysis is divided into four main parts. Part I will provide a brief review of the relevant history of artificial intelligence, image generators, and moral rights in the United States. Part II will focus on the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990, exploring its legislative history, interpretation, and applicability to intangible forms of visual works. Part III will explore the mechanisms of AI and its system, the types of infringements by AI during training and through user manipulation, including conducting related experiments. Lastly, the article aims to clarify if artificial intelligence systems pose a threat to moral rights in the United States.

Part I

Introduction of Generative AI and Image Generator

Artificial intelligence is not something new. Some people would say AI it's already exists from the dawn of the Greek philosophers around 450BCE.¹ Others will give the right to Leonardo de Vinci with its robot knight invention in the 15th century. Nonetheless, exploring carefully with the relevant perspective, the most relevant event drives us directly to the mid of the 20th century, of the publication of "Computer Machinery and Intelligence" by Alan Turing which proposed a test of machine intelligence called the "Imitation Game".² The "Imitation Game," also known as the Turing Test, was introduced by Turing in 1950. It's a method to see if a machine can act as smart as a human. In the test, a judge talks to a human and a machine without seeing them. They communicate through a computer so that looks and sounds don't affect the judge's decision. The judge has to figure out which one is the machine, and who is the human based on how they answer questions. If the judge can't tell the differences, the machine passed the test, showing it has human-like intelligence. This test which was consider a cornerstone experiment at the time, also attracted criticism regarding its ability to accurately measure intelligence or whether passing the test genuinely equates to possessing human-like intelligence.³ One this is surely, that those who underestimate the capability of AI to equate human-like intelligence, probably did not imagine that 70 years later, we will face in front of systems that arguably have already surpass human-like intelligence.

Between Turing test and the releasing of Chat GPT to the public in 2022, Artificial intelligence has made small progress every few years, which most of the progress is behind the eye of the public and happening mostly in the academia and research circles. In early 1980 AI showed fast growth thanks to breakthrough research in academia and the first commercial market system,

¹ Chatzikiyriakidis, E. (2023, February 15). The connection between AI and Ancient Greek Philosophy. See at <https://efxa.org/2023/02/15/the-connection-between-ai-and-ancient-greek-philosophy/>

² A. M. TURING, *Mind*, Volume LIX, Issue 236, October 1950, Pages 433–460 (01 October 1950)

³ John R. Searle, Minds, Brains, and Programs, in *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, vol. 3, at 417-457 (1980); Stevan Harnad, Minds, Machines and Turing: The Indistinguishability of Indistinguishables, U. of Southampton, Highfield, Southampton SO17 1BJ, U.K.

known as “XCON”.⁴ This system is designed to automatically decide how computer components should be assembled in an order, based on the computer needs.⁵ In late 1980s to early 2000s, AI suffered from impeding progress, but everything has changed in the mid-2000s, when the big social media companies have started use AI technologies, also known as algorithm in their social media platforms.⁶ Companies such as Facebook, Twitter (“X”), and Google, have begun use algorithm for advertising and enhancing user experience.⁷ Later on, Apple introduced the virtual assistant “Siri” in 2011⁸. Just five years later, in 2016, “Sophia”, a robot developed by Hanson Robotics, became the first to display a realistic appearance, emotions, and communication capabilities⁹. All these “products” are involving some sort of AI technology, illustrating how AI is embedded in our lives years before the unprecedented system called Open AI (“ChatGPT”) released to the public.¹⁰

Generative AI is define as “a branch of artificial intelligence [(AI)] that enables [computerized systems] to quickly and convincingly create original content ranging from Images and artwork to poetry, music, text, video, dialog, and even computer code.”¹¹ Among the vast capabilities of AI, the one that will be the focus of this article is the Artificial Intelligence Image Generator (“IG”).¹² IG can produce almost anything, leveraging its roots that are deeply connected to the internet. While requiring no specialty or expertise, any 8-year-old child with an internet connection can perform this production by inserting basic instruction to the input of the Image Generator. The most popular programs in the market at this moment, are DALL-E by OpenAI

⁴ Virginia E. Barker & Dennis E. O'Connor, Expert Systems for Configuration at Digital: XCON and Beyond, in 298 Comm. ACM 298, 318 (Mar. 1989).

⁵ Id.

⁶ Chelsea Peterson-Salahuddin & Nicholas Diakopoulos, Negotiated Autonomy: The Role of Social Media Algorithms in Editorial Decision Making, 8 Media & Commc'n 27, pages 27-29 (2020).

⁷ Id at 27.

⁸ Victor Sanchez, The History of Siri and Its Impact on Today's Technology, Routine Hub (Mar. 17, 2023), <https://blog.routinehub.co/the-history-of-siri-and-its-impact-on-todays-technology/>.

⁹ Hanson Robotics, Sophia, <https://www.hansonrobotics.com/sophia/> (last visited May 6, 2024).

¹⁰ Victor M. Palace, WHAT IF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WROTE THIS? ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND COPYRIGHT LAW, 71 Fla. L. Rev. 217, 220-221 (2019).

¹¹ Louis Rosenberg, *Generative AI: The technology of the year for 2022*, Big Think (Dec 20, 2022), <https://bigthink.com/the-present/generative-ai-technology-of-year-2022/> [<https://perma.cc/A3ER-MT8B>].

¹² Ryan Abbott & Elizabeth Rothman, ARTICLE: DISRUPTING CREATIVITY: COPYRIGHT LAW IN THE AGE OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, 75 Fla. L. Rev. 1141, 1152-1153.

that also introduced the Chat GPT feature, Midjourney by Midjourney inc, and Stable Diffusion by Stability AI.¹³ Those programs have given the capability of generating images with great visual details from a person’s imagination, as described in the chat input of the IG.¹⁴ In fact, The production of images by IG are almost endless because of relaying on enormous amount of data contains millions of millions of images, pictures and published online artworks.¹⁵ Generally, Image Generators are trained by millions of images along with millions of other files, which scanned to the dataset by the AI companies, make it possible to every element of expression located on the World Wide Web to be combined in output work.¹⁶ This system that enables to copy artistic “styles”, creating fake news-like images, adding modification or making changes to preexisting works, distortion or mutilation, by accidently or by design, concerns many scholars which view this systems out of control.¹⁷ In legal aspect, image generator raises fundamental concerns in disciplinaries of law, including copyright, privacy, and cybersecurity.¹⁸ Nonetheless, Exploring the history of artificial intelligence shows that U.S. congress confronted with related issues almost 60 years ago. In 1965, a report of the Register of Copyrights brought up three major problems as a result of computer-generated works.¹⁹ All three relevant for today: “registration for computer programs, computer authorship, and automation in the Copyright Office”.²⁰ As a result of the confrontation, congress’ commission provided conclusion that make sure the ownership stays with the user: “computer like a camera or a typewriter, is an inert instrument, capable of functioning only when activated either directly or indirectly by a

¹³ Sabrina Ortiz, Best AI Image Generator, ZDNet (Apr. 9, 2024) available at <https://www.zdnet.com/article/best-ai-image-generator/>.

¹⁴ Michael D. Murray, GENERATIVE AI ART: COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT AND FAIR USE, 26 SMU Sci. & Tech. L. Rev. 259, 260-261.

¹⁵ Rosenberg, supra, note 11.

¹⁶ Id.

¹⁷ Bengio, Yoshua. “AI and Catastrophic Risk”. *Journal of Democracy* 34, no. 4 (October 2023): 111–21.

¹⁸ Palace, supra, note 10 ; see also Murray, supra note 14; See also 5 Nimmer on Copyright § 20.05 (2024).

¹⁹ U.S. COPYRIGHT OFFICE, SIXTY-EIGHTH ANNUAL REPORT OF THE REGISTER OF COPYRIGHTS 5 (1965),

<https://www.copyright.gov/reports/annual/archive/ar-1965.pdf> [<https://perma.cc/E55P-XEUF>] at 4.

²⁰ Id.

human."²¹ Regardless of the commission's conclusion which might "postponed" the problems 60 years ago, Artificial Intelligence has progressed so dramatically up to the extent that even some model required no human input.²² As a matter of fact, it was not until 2017 that Congress initiated proactive measures concerning artificial intelligence by establishing the "Artificial Intelligence Caucus" aimed at enhancing policymakers' awareness. However, no major actions have followed since then.²³ In addition, both the Congress and scholars did not give full of attention to future effects of AI on moral rights framework within the United States, which is the focus of this paper.

Introduction of Moral Rights in the U.S.

Exploring the historical evolution of moral rights within the United States unveils a nuanced conclusion that, in theory, moral rights are recognized for creative works. However, in practical terms, the United States extends a minimal, and arguably non-existent, level of protection for moral rights.²⁴ The idea of moral rights originates from the French law with the concept of "droit moral" and is has been significant part of copyright law in European countries.²⁵ Moral rights for creative works, often referred to the right of *integrity* which gives the author the right to object to any mutilation, distortion, or modification to the original work, and the right of *attribution*, also known as "credit", to be named as the author of the work.²⁶ Within those rights are additional rights, such as the right to prevent others from falsely claiming authorship of the original author's work, the right to withdraw work that has been published, and the right to prohibit any use that could harm the author's reputation. The rationale behind moral rights is to protect the author's good name and reputation.²⁷ Accordingly, any use of the original work in a manner that

²¹ NAT'L COMM'N ON NEW TECH. USES OF COPYRIGHTED WORKS, FINAL REPORT OF THE NATIONAL COMMISSION ON NEW TECHNOLOGICAL USES OF COPYRIGHTED WORKS 44-45 (1978), <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015026832934> [<https://perma.cc/RUA7-AT2J>].

²² Palace, *supra* note 10, at [223-224](#).

²³ *Id.*, at 225.

²⁴ William Belanger, ARTICLE: U.S. COMPLIANCE WITH THE BERNE CONVENTION, 3 *Geo. Mason Ind. L. Rev.* 373, 394.

²⁵ *Id.* at 373, 383.

²⁶ Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *Preserving Personality And Reputational Interests Of Constructed Personas Through Moral Rights: A Blueprint For The Twenty-First Century*, 2001 *U. Ill. L. Rev.* 151, 163.

²⁷ *Oliver v. Meow Wolf, Inc.*, No. 20-237 KK/SCY, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 134942 (D.N.M. Aug. 3, 2023).

mocks or degrades it in the eyes of the author can violate these rights. Moral rights are paramount in Europe, whereas in the U.S., they are not considered a matter of fundamental public policy.²⁸ This difference is due to the U.S. legal tradition, which emphasizes the economic benefits of creative works, in contrast to the European approach that prioritizes the personal rights of artists.²⁹ As a result of those key differences between the U.S. and European countries, the U.S. had being refused for more than 100 years, to sign on major multilateral international agreement: '*Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic works*'.³⁰ The Berne Convention which provided moral rights among others, was one of the main reasons why U.S. had stayed out of this agreement. The Berne Convention established in 1886, based on three basic principles, which designed to provide minimum rights for authors: (1) member parties must give no less rights than they give to their own nationals, (2) principle of "automatic protection" - no requirements of copyright formalities, (3) principle of "Independence" - each member country must protect copyrighted works from other members according to its own laws, regardless of the protection level in the work's home country.³¹ The Berne Convention also provides "moral rights" in Article 6bis of the Convention, relatively at the same level as European standards.³²

While the U.S. was in constant disregard for the Berne Convention, confrontation was inevitable in light of globalization in the mid-1980s, which led the U.S. to decide to join the Berne Convention in the late 1980s.³³ In order to become a party, U.S. implemented the Brene Convention Implementation Act of 1988 that became valid in 1989, making The United States a member party of the Brene Convention.³⁴ Despite the formal action of implementing the Berne Convention, the Congress explicitly declared in the body of the Act that the Berne Convention

²⁸ Llewellyn Joseph Gibbons, Visual Artists Rights Act ("VARA") and the Protection of Digital Works of "Photographic" Art, 11 N.C. J.L. & Tech. 531, 533).

²⁹ Belanger, supra note 24 at 373,383.

³⁰Id at 373,373.

³¹ See the three principle at WIPO website: https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ip/berne/summary_berne.html.

³² Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works art. 6bis, Sept. 9, 1886, as revised at Paris on July 24, 1971, 828 U.N.T.S. 221, available at [WIPO](#).

³³ Peter Burger, THE BERNE CONVENTION: ITS HISTORY AND ITS KEY ROLE IN THE FUTURE., 3 J.L. & TECH. 1, 67.

³⁴ BERNE CONVENTION IMPLEMENTATION ACT OF 1988, 1988 Enacted H.R. 4262, 100 Enacted H.R. 4262, 102 Stat. 2853.

and its obligations are not self-executing is the U.S., that every obligation of the U.S. under the Berne Convention may be performed only pursuant to appropriate domestic law, and that the implementation act along with the current law in the U.S., satisfy the obligations of the U.S., and in adhering to the Berne Convention and no required further legislation.³⁵ Reading the declarations along with reviewing the Berne Convention Implementation Act, indicates that Congress deliberately chose not to incorporate moral rights into the law, because U.S. Congress assumed that the intellectual property framework in the U.S. complies with the Berne Convention and provides sufficient protection for moral rights within its borders.

The Congress' assumption likely stems from the 2nd Circuit ruling *Gilliam v. ABC*, which decided in 1976.³⁶ This case involving, members of the British comedy troupe Monty Python, which sued the American Broadcasting Companies, Inc. (ABC) for editing episodes of "Monty Python's Flying Circus" before their broadcast within the United States. ABC's modifications included cut advertising time slots and removal of content deemed unsuitable for American audiences, which Monty Python argued distorted their work and misrepresented their artistic expression. The court ruled in favor of Monty Python, finding that ABC's alterations significantly changed the character of the work, effectively resulting in a "mutilation" that prejudiced the honor and reputation of the creators (right of integrity). Despite the absence of explicit recognition of moral rights in United States copyright law—a point reiterated by the court—the court relied on Section 43(a) of the Lanham Act, which protects against false designation of origin of goods or services, also known as a 'passing off' claim.³⁷ The court suggested that this statute was intended to prevent misrepresentations that may injure a plaintiff's business or personal reputation. Thus, the court applied this law in a way that determined the editing done by ABC mutilated the original work, resulting in a violation of Section 43(a).³⁸ By utilizing the Lanham Act in this manner, the Second Circuit effectively aligned the rationale of Section 43(a) of the Lanham Act more closely with European standards behind the protection of

³⁵ Id at 2853, 2854.

³⁶ [Gilliam v. ABC, 538 F.2d 14 \(2d Cir. 1976\)](#).

³⁷ 15 U.S.C. § 1125(a) (2022) (Lanham Act § 43(a)).

³⁸ See *Gilliam*, supra note 36, at 14, 24.

an author's moral rights. It is safe to say that this landmark case created the assumption that the U.S. Congress declared that U.S. law adheres to the Berne Convention, including moral rights standards - a reasonable assumption at the time of the implementing act. However, this may no longer be true following the precedent decision of the United States Supreme Court in 2003.³⁹

This case involved Fox Film Corporation, which owned the copyright to the 1940s TV series "Crusade in Europe," based on Dwight D. Eisenhower's memoirs. After these films entered the public domain, Dastar Corp., edited this TV series into a new film called "World War II Campaigns in Europe," without giving credit to Fox Film Corporation or the original creators. The Supreme Court ruled in favor of Dastar, explaining that under the Lanham Act, "origin" refers to the producer of the tangible product sold, not the creators of any preexisting works without attribution ("Credit").⁴⁰ Therefore, as the producer of the new video, Dastar was legally recognized as the origin, exempting them from the need to credit the original series' creators.⁴¹ The court interpretation distinguished from ABC case regarding the claim of "false designation of origin" in section 43(a) of the Lanham act. Per the Supreme Court of the United States, this claim has been intended to prevent consumer confusion, and does not refer to the author's embodiment or idea in the products itself.⁴² The court noted that a contrary decision would undermine Congressional intent, which could have explicitly addressed this issue as it did in the past, at the time of the enactment of the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990.⁴³ Additionally, the court highlighted that such a ruling would raise practical issues, including ambiguity and potential conflicts with U.S. copyright law.⁴⁴ This landmark precedent decision of the U.S. Supreme Court while considering the U.S. congress implementation Act and its assumptions relied on the *Gillam's* case, has risen the proper concern that the United States is not comply with the Brene Convention accordingly to the moral rights it offers subsequent to the Supreme Court decision. Bearing that in mind, the Unites States do provide sort of limited moral rights

³⁹ [Dastar Corp. v. Twentieth Century Fox Film Corp., 539 U.S. 23, 123 S. Ct. 2041 \(2003\)](#)

⁴⁰ Id, at 23, 37, 123 S. Ct. 2041, 2049-50.

⁴¹ Id, at 23, 25, 123 S. Ct. 2041, 2043.

⁴² Id at 23, 37, 123 S. Ct. 2041, 2049.

⁴³ Id, at 23, 25, 123 S. Ct. 2041, 2043.

⁴⁴ Id.

protection for creative works by the power of Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990 (“VARA”), which codified in Title 17.⁴⁵ This Act will stand in the center of this article in respect to moral rights in the U.S.

Part II: Visual Artist Rights Act of 1990

Under VARA, the United States offers only nominal protection of moral rights, which affords independent exclusive rights that can be retained by the author after the copyright in the work has been transferred to a third party.⁴⁶

Under VARA, artists are granted the right of attribution and integrity, which allows them to claim authorship of their work or to disassociate from works they did not create, which is also known as “Credit”.⁴⁷ Additionally, allowing artists to prevent any distortion, mutilation, or modification of their work that could damage their honor, reputation, or good name.⁴⁸ VARA also grants artists the right to protect their works from destruction by third parties.⁴⁹ VARA allows artists to waive their rights, in writing, while clearly stating which VARA rights are being waived.⁵⁰ In contrast, The European standards, do not permit any waiver of moral rights.⁵¹ The enactment of VARA is demonstration of the United States recognition in personal rights, which serving the economic benefits of authors, contrary to the utilitarian incentive rationale which generally priorities in the U.S.⁵²

The Narrow Nature of VARA

Although VARA is based on the same rationale of moral rights as those in the European Union—primarily to prevent actions that insult the author or harm their name, honor, and reputation—the

⁴⁵ 17 U.S.C. § 106A (2018).

⁴⁶ James J. Mastroianni, *The Work Made for Hire Exception to the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990 (VARA): Carter v. Helmsley-Spear, Inc.*, 4 Vill. Sports & Ent. L.J. 417, 417 ; *See also* 2 Melville B. Nimmer, *Nimmer on Copyright*, §§ 8D.67, n.45 (1996).

⁴⁷ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(a)(1) (2007).

⁴⁸ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(a)(2) (2007).

⁴⁹ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(a)(3)(A), (B) (2007).

⁵⁰ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(e)(1) (2007); *Martin v. City of Indianapolis*, 982 F. Supp.625, 636-37 (S.D. Ind. 1997)

⁵¹ European Parliamentary Research Service, *Comparative Law Library Unit, Copyright Law in the EU: Salient Features of Copyright Law Across the EU Member States*, PE 625.126 (June 2018); *see also* Mastroianni, *supra* note 46 at 417.

⁵² Fromer, Jeanne C., *Expressive Incentives in Intellectual Property*, 98 Va. L. Rev. 1745, 1746 (2012).

form of moral rights under VARA in the United States does not provide rights equivalent to those offered by European standards, either in the scope of protection or in the extent of the creative works covered.⁵³

VARA applies only to works of visual art, which defined in Section 101 of the copyright act as: “(1) a painting, drawing, print, or sculpture, existing in a single copy, in a limited edition of 200 copies or fewer..... signed and consecutively numbered by the author... or; (2) a still photographic image produced for exhibition purposes only, existing in a single copy..... signed by the author, or in a limited edition of 200 copies or fewer.....”.⁵⁴ Even stricter, VARA excludes commercial works (made for hire) from its protection and applies only to works of 'fine art'.⁵⁵ Neither the Copyright Act nor the legislators at the time of the enactment of VARA defined the term 'fine art,' possibly intentionally or through neglect. However, Scholars have suggested that fine art is “works of art that are romantically viewed as ‘fine art’, [which have been] touched by the hand of the artists... originals and not reproduced copies of the works of authorship embodied in such artifacts”.⁵⁶ That definition, raises ambiguity whether ‘fine art’ including intangible forms of ‘fine art’, specifically digital art, as work that are entitled to VARA’s protection.⁵⁷ Additionally, Within the definition of visual art, there are two additional requirements that in favor of physical appearance rather intangible forms, the work must be (1) signed and (2) numbered, which stands in favored of physical appearance as well.

The nature of VARA and its definitions, which also serve as requirements for VARA’s protection, illustrate how narrow is the scope of protection for creative works in the U.S, but also raise ambiguity and lack of clarity regarding whether or not VARA’s protection extends to intangible

⁵³ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(b) (2007).

⁵⁴ 17 U.S.C. § 101 (2018).

⁵⁵ Id; See also Gibbons, supra note 28, at 531, 535; see also 2 MELVILLE B. NIMMER & DAVID NIMMER, ON COPYRIGHT § 8D.02[A], at 8D-1 1 (“Moral rights in the United States display a pronounced bias in favor of fine artists - painters, sculptors, photographers and the like.”).

⁵⁶ *Dane Ciolino, Rethinking the Compability of Moral Rights and Fair Use*, 54 *Wash. & Lee L. Rev.* 33, 76-77 (1997).

⁵⁷ Id.

forms of visual art such as digital art or digital fine art.⁵⁸ **Even though this question is not the focus of this article, it is required to clarify this preliminary question, in order to determining whether AI constitutes a threat to moral rights in the U.S. with respect to VARA.** Under this consideration, if VARA’s protection does not extend to digital art or digital reproductions of fine art, either today or in the future, then the use of artificial intelligence in ways that are detrimental to an author’s moral rights in European countries does not pose a threat of violating moral rights in the U.S. Conversely, if VARA does extend to digital art or digital reproductions of fine art, then the threat to the obliteration of moral rights in the U.S. is significant.

Does VARA’s Protection Extend to Intangible Forms of Visual Works?

To address this challenging question, it is important to start with the basics of VARA. Before that, we must acknowledge VARA’s efforts to identify what does not qualify as works of visual art: “...any poster, map, globe, chart, technical drawing, diagram, model, applied art, motion picture or other audiovisual work, book, magazine, newspaper, periodical, data base, electronic information service, electronic [publication](#), or similar [publication](#); ... (ii) any merchandising item (iii)...(B) any [work made for hire](#); or (C) any work not subject to copyright protection under this title”.⁵⁹

In addition, Subsection (c) of VARA contains 3 exceptions to the rights of attribution and integrity, while exception (3) stating that those rights [right of integrity and attribution] “... shall not apply to any reproduction, depiction, portrayal... or in any connection with any item described in subparagraph (A) or (B) of the definition of “[work of visual art](#)” in section 101, and any such reproduction, depiction, portrayal, or other use of a work is not a destruction, distortion, mutilation, or other modification described in paragraph (3) of subsection (a).”⁶⁰ Reading that, without further investigation seems to remove any risk rising from the using Image Generators in connection to works of visual art. Presumably, under this exception, any reproduction by AI that

⁵⁸ Gibbons, supra note 28 at 531, 552; see also Ashley Tarokh, Visual Artists Rights Act (VARA) and the Protection of Digital Embodiments of Artworks, 48 Bost. Intell. Prop. Ass'n 1 at 1, 38 (2016).

⁵⁹ 17 U.S.C. § 101 (2018)

⁶⁰ 17 U.S.C. § 106A(c)(3) (2007)

“allegedly” harm the author’s right of integrity and attribution does not de facto violate VARA’s moral rights. However, by exploring the legislative history of VARA, examining technological advancements and contemporary art, and considering the use of digital tools in fine art, along with interpretations by courts, this is way more uncertain than it look like. In fact, many factors support to the contrary that VARA’s protection indeed extends to digital visual art or digital fine art, including the digital reproduction of such works, under certain circumstances.

Legislation History of VARA

Primarily, the history of VARA supports the notion of protecting digital art, if not at the time of the enactment, at least in the evolving technologies and by community standards in the future.⁶¹ According to the house report 101-504 regarding VARA, courts need to “use common sense and generally accepted standards of the artistic community in determining whether a particular work falls within the scope of the definition”.⁶² This clarification provided by legislators at the time of the enactment demonstrates that the definitions of 'fine art' or 'visual art' in VARA are dynamic, reflecting changes influenced by the evolving community.⁶³ This evolution can be driven by technological innovations and the adoption of new tools for creating fine art and visual art. In this context, works that were not considered fine art at the time of the enactment may now indeed be recognized as fine art or visual art. Consequently, if the community recognizes digital forms of paintings, drawings, sculptures, photographs, and similar works as fine art, then the protection afforded by VARA should extend to moral rights protection to these works.⁶⁴ In addition to that, it is widely accepted that artists are not bound to one medium of physical creation but are allowed to use any form of material and types of media: “Artists may work in a variety of media, and use any number of materials in creating their works. Therefore, whether a particular work falls within the definition should not depend on the medium or materials used.”⁶⁵ In that regard,

⁶¹ H. R. Rep. No. 101-514, at 6919.; see also *Carter v. Helmsley-Spear, Inc.*, 4 Vill. Sports & Ent. L.J. 417, 449 (1997).

⁶² Id at 6921.

⁶³ Peter E. Berlowe et. al., *In This Digital Age, Are We Protecting Tomorrow's "Masterpieces"? Protection of the Moral Rights of the Digital Graphic Artist*, 81-OCT Fla. B.J. 30, 32 (2007).

⁶⁴ Id.

⁶⁵ *Flack v. Friends of Queen Catherine Inc*, 139 F. Supp. 2d 526, 533 (S.D.N.Y. 2001) ; See also Berlowe, supra note 63 ; also Tarokh, supra note 58 at 1,9 (citing H. R. Rep. No. 101-514).

Massachusetts protects intangible forms of fine art by its legislation: “‘fine art’, any original work of visual or graphic art of any media which shall include, but not limited to, any painting, print, drawing, sculpture, craft object, photograph, audio or video tape, film, hologram, or any combination thereof, or recognized quality”.⁶⁶ Scholars like Professor Kwall for example, supports this possibility, arguing that physical appearance is not requirement for moral rights’ protection under VARA.⁶⁷

Community Standards

The fact that the house report 101-504, suggests that visual art definition is subject to influence by the community, indicates that the list exists in VARA not exhaustive.⁶⁸

As far as the community concerns fine art includes variety of forms including intangible or digital ones as fine art or visual art.⁶⁹ Today, fine art is broadly defined as creative work driven by aesthetic, intellectual, or emotional values rather than just physical appearance.⁷⁰ Over time, fine art has moved from traditional forms such as physical sculptures, drawings, carvings and others to include digital art or digital embodiment of fine art, a change driven by technology and culture evolvement.⁷¹ Not only that the medium has changed, but also the process of creating physical art as well. Today, more than ever, creating physical art involves digital technologies such as programs, tools, and apps for creating sketches, designs, or adding modifications and corrections.⁷² Andy Warhol, one of the most popular and influential modern fine art artists in the world, was one of the firsts to take advantage of digital art.⁷³ Warhol pieces of art worth millions

⁶⁶ Mass. Gen. Laws ch. 231, § 85S(b) (2000).

⁶⁷ Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *Preserving Personality And Reputational Interests Of Constructed Personas Through Moral Rights: A Blueprint For The Twenty-First Century*, 2001 U. Ill. L. Rev. 151, 163-164.

⁶⁸ See H. R., supra note 61 at 6921; See also Berlowe, supra note 63.

⁶⁹ See id, Berlowe at 30, 32.

⁷⁰ Gómez-Rincón, C. M. (2023). Art as a spiritual practice. The interplay between artistic creation and spiritual search in seven Colombian artists. *Journal for the Study of Spirituality*, 13(2), 132–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20440243.2023.2243811>; see also Talley, Rob. "The Power of Art: Does Art Really Change the World We Live In?" Art Business News, 22 February 2023, artbusinessnews.com/2023/02/the-power-of-art-does-art-really-change-the-world-we-live-in/.

⁷¹ Can Fine Art Be Digital? Embracing Digital Art is a Rite of Passage." MAC Fine Art Galleries, <https://macfineart.com/can-fine-art-be-digital-embracing-digital-art-is-a-rite-of-passage/>.

⁷² How Technology is Changing the Art World. (n.d.). available at <https://www.artdex.com/how-technology-is-changing-the-art-world-2/>.

⁷³ Id.

of dollars, which considered fine art among the relevant consumers and community.⁷⁴ Warhol is only one example out of many, but those examples illustrates the shift of the community's standards to the point of recognition digital artworks as "pure"(fine) art because they can express complex ideas and provoke deep emotional reactions, just like physical forms.⁷⁵ Even art schools that are strict and conservative regarding their teaching ways have changed their methods in order to keep up with technology.⁷⁶ For example, institutions like the Corcoran College of Art and Design in Washington, D.C., the University of Miami, and the College of Visual Arts in St. Paul, Minnesota, offer a variety of technological graphic courses, which some of them are requirement in the curriculum.⁷⁷ These courses, which include graphic design, electronic media, digital imaging, and other related programs, reflect the diverse tools and techniques required or recommended in their educational programs.⁷⁸ By community standards, the inclusion of certain types of digital art in the definition of fine art is inevitable.

The Language of VARA and Court Interpretation

Analyzing the language of VARA itself provides a similar conclusion. Under VARA, still photographic images, which undoubtedly produced by machine entitled to moral rights protection: "a work of visual art is – (1).....; or (2) still photographic image produced for exhibition purposes only.....".⁷⁹ That stands in favor of granting protection to digital works of fine art, and proves that fine art artworks are not required to be created only by hand. VARA also extends its protection to the copies of this photograph. In the case of physical painting, drawing, print, or fabricated sculptures in 200 copies or fewer, those copies most of the time are not produced by hand 199 times, rather by the help of machines such as 3D printers, computer and alike. Rather than the requirement of numbering the works and signed on them, which true for all works of visual art under VARA, photographic images, which are relevant the most for the sake

⁷⁴ Pogrebin, R. (2022, May 9). Warhol's Shot Sage Blue Marilyn Sells for \$195 Million. *The New York Times*.

<https://www.nytimes.com/2022/05/09/arts/design/warhol-auction-marilyn-monroe.html>

⁷⁵ Can Fine Art Be Digital? Embracing Digital Art is a Rite of Passage." MAC Fine Art Galleries, <https://macfineart.com/can-fine-art-be-digital-embracing-digital-art-is-a-rite-of-passage/>.

⁷⁶ See Berlowe, supra note 63.

⁷⁷ Id.

⁷⁸ Id.

⁷⁹ 17 U.S.C. § 101 (2018).

of this article, require to establish another prerequisite for VARA's protection: that the image will be produced "for exhibition purposes only".⁸⁰

Interpretation of this term is not an easy task. As a matter of fact, most of the attention regarding this term focuses on the interpretation of the author's intent rather than the definition itself. According to scholars and courts interpretations, if the photograph was taken by the author's intent for 'exhibition purposes only', VARA extends to that copy.⁸¹ The District Court of Columbia states that even though it appears that this requirement distinguish between amateur photographers taking pictures as visitors, and an artists, this question is challenging.⁸² Professor Nimmer agrees suggesting that this meant to prevent from every pictures taken by random people to qualify as a still photographic image production protected by VARA.⁸³ In that regard, Professor Gibbons has added a caveat, arguing that this limitation is not solely true. Production for exhibition purposes often occurs later, and even a 'negative copy' (picture taken by others) could be produced for exhibition purposes as a work of visual art in its own right, since it is fixed in a tangible medium of expression.⁸⁴

Bearing this in mind, what would be deemed to "exhibition purposes only" in order to entitled to qualify for VARA's protection. Surprisingly, VARA does not define that term. However, exploring the literature history of the term suggests that the definition is outdated, relying on remnants of traditional exhibition methods from the past and failing to keep up with technological advancements and contemporary forms of exhibition. Considering the nature of fine art, scholars argue that "exhibition purposes" refers solely to the display of art in museums, galleries, and art displays.⁸⁵ This definition, brought directly from the past century, makes it significantly primitive. Modern meaning can favoring any type of public display as set forth in the copyright act: "To display a work means to show a copy of it, either directly or by means of

⁸⁰ Id.

⁸¹ *Lilley v. Stout*, 384 F. Supp. 2d 83, 86 (D.D.C. 2005); See also Gibbons, *supra* note 28, at 531, 534-535.

⁸² See *Lilley*, at 83, 87.

⁸³ See NIMMER ON COPYRIGHT, *supra* note 18, at § 8D.06[A][1].

⁸⁴ See, Gibbons, *supra* note 28, at 531, 538 (citing *See Flack v. Friends of Queen Catherine, Inc.*, 139 F. Supp. 2d 526, 533 (S.D.N.Y. 2001) and, H.R. REP. No. 101-514, *supra* note 4, at 11).

⁸⁵ JULES ADELIN, ET AL., ADELIN'S ART DICTIONARY 153 (1891)

a film, slide, television image, or any other device or process or, in the case of a motion picture or other audiovisual work, to show individual images nonsequentially”.⁸⁶ Furthermore, according to the house report: “the nature or location of the exhibition is not relevant to the determination of whether the photograph is produced only for exhibition purposes”.⁸⁷ To that matter, professor Gibbons concluded that: “both a digital camera image resulting in a photographic print fixed on a tangible medium intended for exhibition, and a digital camera photograph resulting in a virtual digital image displayed by a machine or device for exhibition may equally meet VARA's requirement that the photograph be created solely for exhibition purposes”.⁸⁸ Professor Gibbons states that as long as the digital work qualify the statutory requirements of VARA, digital work should be protected under VARA even if it sold in additional picture frame, USB drive, or through digital downloading.⁸⁹ Recently, a case decided by the District Court of California appears to acknowledge that displaying a photograph on social media solely for exhibition purposes can satisfy the requirements of VARA: “*Thus, for Plaintiffs to meet the definition of work of visual art, it must have limited Perez’s[defendant] use of the photograph on social media to only exhibition purposes, rather than permitting other types of non-commercial purposes....*”.⁹⁰ Despite the rare opportunity for the court to clarify whether digital works are covered under VARA, the court chose not to address the question: “*The court need not determine at this time whether a digital photograph is covered under VARA, or whether the allegedly unauthorized uses of the photograph fall outside of VARA’s Scope*”.⁹¹

Therefore, remains some dust regarding the term “exhibition purposes only”, and if it includes digital display, or other intangible forms. Fair to say, that definition of "exhibition purposes only" is somewhat outdated. Nowadays, public displays and art exhibitions frequently occur online. *Perez’s* case is a perfect example of digital photographs of fine art display online, blurring the line between traditional exhibition and modern intangible ones. A quick search on Facebook

⁸⁶ See Berlowe, *supra* note 63 at 32.

⁸⁷ See H.R. REP. No. 101-514, *supra* note 61.

⁸⁸ See, Gibbons, *supra* note 28, at 531, 546.

⁸⁹ *Id.*

⁹⁰ Hexlastudios v. Perez, No. CV 23-3168-GW-KSx, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 226129 (C.D. Cal. Dec. 15, 2023).

⁹¹ *Id.*

reveals thousands of art groups filled with enthusiasts fascinated by the art world, where dozens of visual works are displayed daily. Does this qualify as "exhibition purposes" under VARA? It is difficult to determine. However, it might be less ambiguity regarding online exhibitions conducted annually by galleries and art museums in recent years.⁹² Although there is acceptance among scholars that digital art entitled or should be entitled to VARA's protection, courts did not have the opportunity to address this issue properly, or when it has, court dismissed the opportunity.⁹³ On the other hand, it is important to mention that there are arguments supporting the notion that VARA was not intended to protect digital art, but only physical works.⁹⁴ The requirements of VARA to number and sign additional copies as a prerequisite for the protection of moral rights to those copies also stands in favor of physical appearance under VARA.⁹⁵ Although in *Perez*, the court did not dwell on or reject the plaintiffs' argument that the digital photographs were signed and numbered with unique metadata digital signatures, it is uncertain what would other courts will decide.⁹⁶

In closing this section, This article contends that rejection of moral rights for digital works, will not only disincentive the utilitarian benefits of the artists, but also will empty and dilute VARA's effectiveness, which is to grants authors personal rights to stop and prevent from any insulting towards the author's name or reputation by using his or her piece of art harmfully.⁹⁷ In that regard, this is hard to imagine the judicial system would ignoring VARA claim arguing infringements of the rights of integrity and attribution in case involving museum that by accidentally or by design, did not include the author's name on the work, or added modification,

⁹² Smithsonian Institution, Online Exhibitions, at <https://www.si.edu/exhibitions/online> (4/28/2024); see also USC Fisher Museum of Art, Virtual Exhibitions, at <https://fisher.usc.edu/exhibitions/virtual-exhibitions/>(4/28/2024); also California Museum, Online Exhibition, at <https://californiamuseum.org/exhibitions/online/> (4/28/2024).

⁹³ Nathan Brown, *VARA Rights Get a Second Life*, 11 J. High Tech. L. 280 (2011); see also Gibbons, *supra* 28 at 531, 552 ; Tarokh, *supra* note 58 at 1, 38; See Berlowe, *supra* note 63 at 32 ; See also *Hexlastudios v. Perez*, No. CV 23-3168-GW-KSx, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 226129 (C.D. Cal. Dec. 15, 2023).

⁹⁴Id.

⁹⁵ 17 U.S.C. § 101 (definition of "work of visual art").

⁹⁶ See Gibbons, *supra* note 28 at 531, 552 ; see Tarokh, *supra* note 58 at 38.

⁹⁷ Miernicki, M., Ng (Huang Ying), I. Artificial intelligence and moral rights. *AI & Soc* 36, 319–329 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-020-01027-6>; See also *Oliver v. Meow Wolf, Inc.*, No. 20-237 KK/SCY, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 134942 (D.N.M. Aug. 3, 2023).

distortion or mutilation to that work, on a virtual exhibit occurred online. If that is true, as we see in *Perez's case*, any publication online, in the relevant circles, including social media, online exhibits, digital museums, websites dedicated to art displays, and alike, would qualify or should be qualified as “exhibition purposes only”.

Taking this into account, the reproduction of images by an AI Image Generator (through user interaction) and their subsequent publication—whether accidental or intentional, by the user or the image generator (AI)—in venues deemed for exhibition purposes only, can theoretically violate authors’ moral rights under VARA.

Part III: The AI Mechanisms Behind Moral Rights Infringement

To explain how the mechanism or system of an Artificial Intelligence Image Generator works, in a way that enables infringement of moral rights, it is necessary to divide the analysis into two types of infringements. First, infringement committed by the Artificial Intelligence as a result of system training. Second, infringement committed by the Artificial Intelligence Image Generator through human manipulation (input).

Infringement by AI Training

Although AI has received full of attention from scholars across the spectrum, experts are still struggling to pinpoint how exactly AI training occurs.⁹⁸ However, scholars do know that AI systems depend on enormous amounts of data to train their systems, which enables the AI system to predict patterns and desired outcomes.⁹⁹

The large data, containing millions of files, images, artworks, texts, copyrighted and

⁹⁸ Id. see also Cal Newport, What We Still Don't Know About How AI Is Trained, *The New Yorker* (2023) available at <https://www.newyorker.com/news/daily-comment/what-we-still-dont-know-about-how-ai-is-trained>.

⁹⁹ Amal Joby, What is Training Data? How It's Used in Machine Learning, *G2* (July 30, 2021), <https://learn.g2.com/training-data> ; See also Andrew W. Torrance & Bill Tomlinson, Training is Everything: Artificial Intelligence, Copyright, and "Fair Training", 128 *Dick. L. Rev.* 233, 242.

uncopyrighted works, as well as conversations from community forums, is utilized to enhance AI systems, enabling them to demonstrate human-like intelligence and to provide optimal outcomes in response to user’s input.¹⁰⁰ It is presumed that the use of millions of copyrighted works, including thousands of visual art pieces protected by VARA, for training purposes constitutes consistent infringement of moral rights.¹⁰¹ This is because AI companies neither compensate the original creators nor attribute the authors' works.¹⁰² There is no disputes among scholars that using millions of copyrighted works for training purposes, AI systems under highly probability of prima facie copyright infringement as well.¹⁰³ At the same time, scholars are in dispute regarding whether AI training will constitute eventually “fair use”.¹⁰⁴ Some argue that AI functions as human, consumed and inspired by knowledge, while AI is not directly interfered with copyrighted works, AI using images during training constitutes fair use.¹⁰⁵ Others, reject that argument saying that the use of AI in copyrighted works for training purposes is a misappropriation of owners' intellectual property, leads to market harm, and creating unauthorized derivative works.¹⁰⁶ Beyond the disputes among scholars, there is litigation challenge for plaintiffs proving copying “in fact” by the AI during its training.¹⁰⁷ *Stability AI’s* case, which decided recently, illustrates the challenge of a plaintiff to identify the works that used in training that cause the AI copying plaintiff’s artistic style. The case involved a visual digital artists, allege that their works were used for training purposes by the AI system in addition to created unauthorized derivative works with same artistic “style” to the plaintiffs.¹⁰⁸ Court, requested the plaintiffs to identify the specific images that were training by the system that according to their argument infringed and copying their artistic “style”.¹⁰⁹ According to *Stability*

¹⁰⁰ Id.

¹⁰¹ James Vincent, *The Scary Truth About AI*, The Verge (2023), available at <https://www.theverge.com/23444685/generative-ai-copyright-infringement-legal-fair-use-training-data>.

¹⁰² Id.

¹⁰³ 5 Nimmer on Copyright § 20.05 (2024) ; see also Torrance & Tomlinson, supra note 99 at 233, 247.

¹⁰⁴ Id, Torrance & Tomlinson, supra note 99 at, 233, 244.

¹⁰⁵ Id.

¹⁰⁶ See Jessica L. Gillotte, Note, Copyright Infringement in AI Generated Artworks, 53 U.C. Davis L. Rev. 2655, 2679-91 (2020).

¹⁰⁷ *Andersen v. Stability AI Ltd.*, No. 23-cv-00201-WHO, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 194324 (N.D. Cal. Oct. 30, 2023).

¹⁰⁸ Id, at 23.

¹⁰⁹ Id, at 11.

AI's court, providing examples of works that were found in training data base was not specific enough to indicate copying.¹¹⁰ The court allowed the plaintiffs amend their complaint.¹¹¹ In the light of *Stability AI's* case, for an infringement to be recognized under VARA, it must involve a notable work that has been used in a manner clearly associated with a specific artist. This requirement becomes increasingly difficult to meet with AI image generators and machine learning systems, as these technologies often use thousands of images and styles in ways that obscure the connections to individual artists. Nonetheless, cases involving moral rights might have a lower threshold for infringement during training. The mere use of an image for training purposes and its presence in a database without attribution can be sufficient to constitute an infringement of moral rights, even if it does not infringe U.S. copyright.

Infringement by the User

Given the complexities involved in identifying infringing works during AI training, there is less complexity in cases involving user manipulation. By using Image Generators, Users can produce endless versions of artworks, some of them relying on, or “inspired” from copyrighted visual works such as painting, drawing, photographs and alike, which some elements from these works can resembled in the user’s output chat.¹¹² Considering unique modifications by the user's imagination and the AI system alterations, collectively might result in distortions, mutilations, or absent of attribution, that infringes moral rights.

It is enough for a user to ask AI image generator to create women portrait with the style of Leonardo de Vinci in order to produce two images that are violate de Vinci’s moral rights in its Mona Lisa’s work, if his moral rights would have valid today:

¹¹⁰ Id. (plaintiffs provided examples of their works locating on this data base - https://haveibeen trained.com/?search_text=sar, at 30.

¹¹¹ Id.

¹¹² See Murray, *supra* note 14.

I've generated two new images that aim for a closer resemblance to Leonardo da Vinci's style, focusing on a more realistic and classic portrayal. You can see the enhanced details and the approach in the images above. Please take a look and see if these meet your expectations.

These images include the text attached to them produced by the AI system called DALL-E powered by OpenAI.¹¹³ The text, resembled the request of the user in addition to the “artistic” approach by the system.¹¹⁴ In any time while chatting with the DALL-E the system was not requested to create portrait of Mona Lisa or similar to that, rather only portrait of a women in Leonardo da Vinci’s style. This demonstration highlights fundamental issues related to copyright infringement in case those images would have been copyrighted, which are not the focus of this article. However, from a moral rights perspective, pretending that Leonardo da Vinci still holds moral rights to his paintworks, the AI system along with the user’s manipulation created distortions, mutilation, and modifications to Mona Lisa’s artwork, which reflect by the “modern look”, different hair, colors, light, “smoother” picture, and facial modifications. The AI system created these modifications and distortions in the Mona Lisa paintwork without even naming it. Presumably, the image generator assumed, that the user, by asking for “women portrait” in Leonardo Da Vinci “style” referred to Mona Lisa work, that undoubtably is the most famous

¹¹³ <https://chat.openai.com/g/g-2fkFE8rbu-dall-e>.

¹¹⁴ Created by DALL-E in May 1, 2024, by the input of the author, Aviel Shimoni.

women portrait of Leonardo Da Vinci, but far from by the only women portrait in his great collection.¹¹⁵ This “experiment” indicates two primary assertions. First, AI Image Generators can create modification, distortions, and mutilation in specific works, without naming the same specific works. Second, the fact that AI system chose Mona Lisa portrait rather than other women portraits by Leonardo Da Vinci, indicates that the AI systems are subject to manipulation by the knowledge and information over the internet. Considering that, “flooding” the dataset or the internet itself with specific images, files, texts, narratives, or simply every piece of information, in large scales, can manipulate the system producing output resembled the most recognizable and notable piece of content locating in the system database. Notwithstanding, infringement of moral rights would occur if the image produced and used by the AI or by the user for “exhibition purpose only”. Element that can be established by the user in many art’s circles as we mentioned earlier in this article.

Although this experiment illustrates AI patterns and processes, it required clarification. This experiment involved somewhat explicit manipulation by the user – “creating Leonardo da Vinci’s style women portrait”, which some people would say that the instruction that were given to the AI image Generator is rather specific to be deemed or proves creating distortions or modifications to specific work from scratch. It is true, while this scenario required less explicit intent compared to what is required with other technological tools, (photo editor, photoshop and alike) the same level of infringement can occur by users utilizing other technological tools available over the past 30 years. In that specific regard, AI does not pose a greater threat than what users can achieve with edit programs, aside from the ease and reduced expertise required in using AI. Nevertheless, unique situations may arise where an AI system, requested by users to create art without specific instructions, reproduces existing works without attribution or adding modification and distortion to existing works in a cover of “new” artwork produced by Image Generators. Such cases, are not hypothetical, and already happened in *Stability AI’s* case noted

¹¹⁵ Frazzoni, Maria. "Women in Leonardo da Vinci's Portraits." DailyArt Magazine, 30 April 2024, dailyartmagazine.com/da-vincis-female-representation/.

earlier, involving AI image generator, copying artistic “style” with no specific instructions dealing with any information regarding the plaintiffs.¹¹⁶

Conclusion

Although the article attempts to remove uncertainty on whether Artificial Intelligence and Image generators pose a threat to moral rights in the United States, many questions remain unanswered. It is unclear whether the Visual Artists Rights Act (VARA) applies to digital visual artworks, or if AI training and production by Image Generators will be “fair use” – both are fundamental questions directly effects on the status of moral rights in the United States.

Unfortunately, courts have not addressed these questions, when presented with the opportunity, they have chosen not to do so. The legislative history of VARA which regulate moral rights in the United States, does not give answer as well, except of, arguably, favoring dynamic and community standard presumptive. Bearing that in mind, there is no disputes that certain people in the community accept and consider digital art as fine art. Many scholars support the notion that VARA includes digital works, while many other do not. On top of that, references to VARA and AI by scholars are scarce, and among those discussing copyright and AI training, the majority believe such use will constitute fair use.¹¹⁷

While “fair use” is a fundamental question regarding copyright infringement, this is raises further complexities regarding moral rights, which is intended to protect different aspects of authors’ rights - personal rights. If an artist's work is distorted or mutilated in a way that could harm their reputation or honor, claiming that such use was “fair use” does not necessarily negate the violation of the artist's moral rights. In that sense, it is uncertain what the outcome would be in cases of VARA violations, using Image Generators, involving “fair use” defense. Furthermore, some artists might argue that if production by Image Generators constitutes "fair use", it

¹¹⁶ See, *Stability AI*, supra note 107.

¹¹⁷ Copyright Infringement in AI-Generated Artworks, 53 U.C. Davis L. Rev. 2655 ; see also 5 Nimmer on Copyright § 20.05 (2024) ; see also *Authors Guild, Inc. v. HathiTrust*, 755 F.3d 87 (2d Cir. 2014); See Matthew Sag, *The New Legal Landscape for Text Mining and Machine Learning*, J. Copyright Soc'y. U.S.A. 66 (2019); See also Henderson, Peter and Li, Xuechen and Jurafsky, Dan and Hashimoto, Tatsunori and Lemley, Mark A. and Liang, Percy, *Foundation Models and Fair Use* (March 27, 2023). Stanford Law and Economics Olin Working Paper No. 584.

inherently contradicts the purposes of VARA, which is intended to prevent any insult to the authors. Additionally, the fact that the "insult" occurs online and not in the physical hall of a museum might not be convincing, especially as digital publications and fine art exhibitions become more common today. Lastly, the experiment discussed in this article demonstrates conclusively that there is a significant risk of moral rights infringement when using artificial intelligence-based image generators, which could potentially threaten moral rights in the U.S., even within the limited framework presented in the "land of liberty".

Reference List

Federal Statutes

15 U.S.C. § 1125(a) (2022) (Lanham Act § 43(a)).

17 U.S.C. § 101 (2018).

17 U.S.C. § 106A (1990) (Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990).

International Agreements

Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, September 9, 1886, revised at Paris July 24, 1971, 1161 U.N.T.S. 3.

State Statutes

Mass. Gen. Laws ch. 231, § 85S(b) (2000).

Supreme Court Cases

Dastar Corp. v. Twentieth Century Fox Film Corp., 539 U.S. 23, 123 S. Ct. 2041 (2003).

Federal Courts of Appeals Cases:

Gilliam v. ABC, 538 F.2d 14 (2d Cir. 1976).

Authors Guild, Inc. v. HathiTrust, 755 F.3d 87 (2d Cir. 2014).

Federal District Court Cases

Martin v. City of Indianapolis, 982 F. Supp. 625, 636-37 (S.D. Ind. 1997).

Flack v. Friends of Queen Catherine Inc., 139 F. Supp. 2d 526, 533 (S.D.N.Y. 2001).

Lilley v. Stout, 384 F. Supp. 2d 83, 86 (D.D.C. 2005).

Oliver v. Meow Wolf, Inc., No. 20-237 KK/SCY, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 134942 (D.N.M. Aug. 3, 2023).

Hexlastudios v. Perez, No. CV 23-3168-GW-KSx, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 226129 (C.D. Cal. Dec. 15, 2023).

Andersen v. Stability AI Ltd., No. 23-cv-00201-WHO, 2023 U.S. Dist. LEXIS 194324 (N.D. Cal. Oct. 30, 2023).

Other Court Cases

Carter v. Helmsley-Spear, Inc., 4 Vill. Sports & Ent. L.J. 417, 449 (1997).

Legislative Materials

- Berne Convention Implementation Act of 1988, 1988 Enacted H.R. 4262, 100 Enacted H.R. 4262, 102 Stat. 2853.
 - [WIPO](#)
- H.R. Rep. No. 101-514, at 6919 (1990) *Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990*
 -
- U.S. COPYRIGHT OFFICE, SIXTY-EIGHTH ANNUAL REPORT OF THE REGISTER OF COPYRIGHTS 5 (1965),
 - <https://www.copyright.gov/reports/annual/archive/ar-1965.pdf> [<https://perma.cc/E55P-XEUF>]
- NAT'L COMM'N ON NEW TECH. USES OF COPYRIGHTED WORKS, FINAL REPORT OF THE NATIONAL COMMISSION ON NEW TECHNOLOGICAL USES OF COPYRIGHTED WORKS 44-45 (1978).

Secondary Materials

- European Parliamentary Research Service, Comparative Law Library Unit, Copyright Law in the EU: Salient Features of Copyright Law Across the EU Member States, PE 625.126 (June 2018)
 - [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2018/625126/EPRS_STU\(2018\)625126_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2018/625126/EPRS_STU(2018)625126_EN.pdf)
- JULES ADELINE, ET AL., ADELINE'S ART DICTIONARY 153 (1891).
 - https://books.google.com/books/about/Adeline_s_Art_Dictionary.html?id=vooZAAAAYAAJ
- Ryan Abbott & Elizabeth Rothman, ARTICLE: DISRUPTING CREATIVITY: COPYRIGHT LAW IN THE AGE OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, 75 Fla. L. Rev. 1141, 1152-1153.
 - [ARTICLE: DISRUPTING CREATIVITY: COPYRIGHT LAW IN THE AGE OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, 75 Fla. L. Rev. 1141](#)
- William Belanger, ARTICLE: U.S. COMPLIANCE WITH THE BERNE CONVENTION, 3 Geo. Mason Ind. L. Rev. 373, 394.
 - [ARTICLE: U.S. COMPLIANCE WITH THE BERNE CONVENTION, 3 Geo. Mason Ind. L. Rev. 373](#)
- [Peter Burger, THE BERNE CONVENTION: ITS HISTORY AND ITS KEY ROLE IN THE FUTURE., 3 J.L. & TECH. 1, 67 \(1988\).](#)

- [ARTICLE: THE BERNE CONVENTION: ITS HISTORY AND ITS KEY ROLE IN THE FUTURE., 3 J.L. & TECH. 1](#)
- Virginia E. Barker & Dennis E. O'Connor, Expert Systems for Configuration at Digital: XCON and Beyond, in 298 Comm. ACM 298, 318 (Mar. 1989).
 - <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/62065.62067>
- Nathan Brown, *VARA Rights Get a Second Life*, 11 J. High Tech. L. 280 (2011)
 - <https://cpb-use1.wpmucdn.com/sites.suffolk.edu/dist/5/1153/files/2018/02/Brown-VARA-Rights-Get-a-Second-Life-29suo80.pdf>
- Fromer, Jeanne C., Expressive Incentives in Intellectual Property, 98 Va. L. Rev. 1745, 1746 (2012).
 - <https://virginialawreview.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/1745.pdf>
- Dane Ciolino, Rethinking the Compability of Moral Rights and Fair Use, 54 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 33, 76-77 (1997).
 - <https://scholarlycommons.law.wlu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1608&context=wlulr>
- Llewellyn Joseph Gibbons, Visual Artists Rights Act ("VARA") and the Protection of Digital Works of "Photographic" Art, 11 N.C. J.L. & Tech. 531, 533).
 - [ARTICLE: Visual Artists Rights Act \("VARA"\) and the Protection of Digital Works of "Photographic" Art, 11 N.C. J.L. & Tech. 531.](#)
- Jessica L. Gillotte, Note, Copyright Infringement in AI Generated Artworks, 53 U.C. Davis L. Rev. 2655, 2679-91 (2020).
 - https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3657423
- Stevan Harnad, Minds, Machines and Turing: The Indistinguishability of Indistinguishables, U. of Southampton, Highfield, Southampton SO17 1BJ, U.K.
 - [Stevan Harnad, Minds, Machines and Turing: The Indistinguishability of Indistinguishables, U. of Southampton, Highfield, Southampton SO17 1BJ, U.K.](#)
- Henderson, Peter and Li, Xuechen and Jurafsky, Dan and Hashimoto, Tatsunori and Lemley, Mark A. and Liang, Percy, Foundation Models and Fair Use (March 27, 2023). Stanford Law and Economics Olin Working Paper No. 584.
 - <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4404340>
- Roberta Rosenthal Kwall, *Preserving Personality And Reputational Interests Of Constructed Personas Through Moral Rights: A Blueprint For The Twenty-First Century*, 2001 U. Ill. L. Rev. 151, 163.

- [SYMPOSIUM: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY CHALLENGES IN THE NEXT CENTURY:ARTICLE PRESERVING PERSONALITY AND REPUTATIONAL INTERESTS OF CONSTRUCTED PERSONAS THROUGH MORAL RIGHTS: A BLUEPRINT FOR THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY, 2001 U. Ill. L. Rev. 151](#)
- Michael D. Murray, GENERATIVE AI ART: COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT AND FAIR USE, 26 SMU Sci. & Tech. L. Rev. 259, 260-261.
- [Articles: GENERATIVE AI ART: COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT AND FAIR USE, 26 SMU Sci. & Tech. L. Rev. 259](#)
- James J. Mastroianni, *The Work Made for Hire Exception to the Visual Artists Rights Act of 1990 (VARA): Carter v. Helmsley-Spear, Inc.*, 4 Vill. Sports & Ent. L.J. 417, 417
 - <https://digitalcommons.law.villanova.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1232&context=msl>
i
- Miernicki, M., Ng (Huang Ying), I. Artificial intelligence and moral rights. *AI & Soc* 36, 319–329 (2021).
 - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-020-01027-6>
- 5 Nimmer on Copyright § 20.05 (2024).
- 2 Melville B. Nimmer, *Nimmer on Copyright*, §§ 8D.67, n.45 (1996).
 - <https://store.lexisnexis.com/products/nimmer-on-copyright-skuusSku10441>
- Gómez-Rincón, C. M. (2023). Art as a spiritual practice. The interplay between artistic creation and spiritual search in seven Colombian artists. *Journal for the Study of Spirituality*, 13(2), 132–146.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1080/20440243.2023.2243811>
- Victor M. Palace, WHAT IF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WROTE THIS? ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND COPYRIGHT LAW, 71 Fla. L. Rev. 217, 220-221 (2019).
 - [ARTICLE: WHAT IF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WROTE THIS? ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND COPYRIGHT LAW, 71 Fla. L. Rev. 217](#)
- Louis Rosenberg, *Generative AI: The technology of the year for 2022*, Big Think (Dec 20,2022)
 - <https://bigthink.com/the-present/generative-ai-technology-of-year-2022/> [<https://perma.cc/A3ER-MT8B>].
- Matthew Sag, *The New Legal Landscape for Text Mining and Machine Learning*, J. Copyright Soc'y. U.S.A. 66 (2019).
 - https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3331606

- John R. Searle, Minds, Brains, and Programs, in *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, vol. 3, at 417-457 (1980).
 - <https://home.csulb.edu/~cwallis/382/readings/482/searle.minds.brains.programs.bbs.1980.pdf>.
- Chelsea Peterson-Salahuddin & Nicholas Diakopoulos, Negotiated Autonomy: The Role of Social Media Algorithms in Editorial Decision Making, 8 *Media & Commc'n* 27, pages 27-29 (2020).
 - <https://www.cogitatiopress.com/mediaandcommunication/article/view/3001/1630>
- A. M. TURING, *Mind*, Volume LIX, Issue 236, October 1950, Pages 433–460 (01 October 1950)
 - <https://academic.oup.com/mind/article/LIX/236/433/986238>
- Andrew W. Torrance & Bill Tomlinson, Training is Everything: Artificial Intelligence, Copyright, and "Fair Training", 128 *Dick. L. Rev.* 233, 242.
 - <https://ideas.dickinsonlaw.psu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1189&context=dlr>
- Ashley Tarokh, Visual Artists Rights Act (VARA) and the Protection of Digital Embodiments of Artworks, 48 *Bost. Intell. Prop. Ass'n* 1 at 1, 38 (2016).
 - <https://newsletter.bipla.org/visual-artists-rights-act-vara-and-the-protection>

Magazine & Newspapers

- Peter E. Berlowe et. al., *In This Digital Age, Are We Protecting Tomorrow's "Masterpieces"?* *Protection of the Moral Rights of the Digital Graphic Artist*, 81-OCT *Fla. B.J.* 30, 32 (2007).
 - <https://www.floridabar.org/the-florida-bar-journal/in-this-digital-age-are-we-protecting-tomorrows-masterpieces-protection-of-the-moral-rights-of-the-digital-graphic-artist/>
- Chatzikyriakidis, E. (2023, February 15). “The connection between AI and Ancient Greek Philosophy”.
 - See at <https://efxa.org/2023/02/15/the-connection-between-ai-and-ancient-greek-philosophy/>.
- Amal Joby, What is Training Data? How It's Used in Machine Learning, *G2* (July 30, 2021)
 - <https://learn.g2.com/training-data>
- Frazzoni, Maria. "Women in Leonardo da Vinci's Portraits." *DailyArt Magazine*, 30 April 2024
 - <https://www.dailyartmagazine.com/da-vincis-female-representation/>
- Sabrina Ortiz, Best AI Image Generator, *ZDNet* (Apr. 9, 2024)
 - available at <https://www.zdnet.com/article/best-ai-image-generator/>.

- Talley, Rob. "The Power of Art: Does Art Really Change the World We Live In?" Art Business News, 22 February 2023
 - artbusinessnews.com/2023/02/the-power-of-art-does-art-really-change-the-world-we-live-in/.
- Pogrebin, R. (2022, May 9). Warhol's Shot Sage Blue Marilyn Sells for \$195 Million. *The New York Times*.
 - <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/05/09/arts/design/warhol-auction-marilyn-monroe.html>
- Hanson Robotics, Sophia Bio, (last visited May 6, 2024).
 - <https://www.hansonrobotics.com/sophia/>
- Victor Sanchez, The History of Siri and Its Impact on Today's Technology, Routine Hub (Mar. 17, 2023):
 - <https://blog.routinehub.co/the-history-of-siri-and-its-impact-on-todays-technology/>
- James Vincent, *The Scary Truth About AI*, The Verge (2023)
 - available at <https://www.theverge.com/23444685/generative-ai-copyright-infringement-legal-fair-use-training-data>.
- Bengio, Yoshua. "AI and Catastrophic Risk". *Journal of Democracy* 34, no. 4 (October 2023): 111–21.
 - <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/articles/ai-and-catastrophic-risk/>

Electronic Sources

- Can Fine Art Be Digital? Embracing Digital Art is a Rite of Passage." MAC Fine Art Galleries
 - <https://macfineart.com/can-fine-art-be-digital-embracing-digital-art-is-a-rite-of-passage/>.
- Cal Newport, What We Still Don't Know About How AI Is Trained, *The New Yorker* (2023)
 - available at <https://www.newyorker.com/news/daily-comment/what-we-still-dont-know-about-how-ai-is-trained>.
- How Technology is Changing the Art World. (n.d.).
 - available at <https://www.artdex.com/how-technology-is-changing-the-art-world-2/>.
- Smithsonian Institution, Online Exhibitions
 - available at <https://www.si.edu/exhibitions/online> (4/28/2024);
- USC Fisher Museum of Art, Virtual Exhibitions
 - Available at [https://fisher.usc.edu/exhibitions/virtual-exhibitions/\(4/28/2024\);](https://fisher.usc.edu/exhibitions/virtual-exhibitions/(4/28/2024);)
- California Museum, Online Exhibition

- Available at <https://californiamuseum.org/exhibitions/online/> (4/28/2024).